

Preparation and Characterisation of Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Transition Elements. Part I. Complexes of Copper II

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The reaction between Copper(II) phthalate in absolute ethanol with some aromatic and chelating diamines produces complexes of type $[\text{Cu}(\text{phth})\text{am}_2 \text{ or } \text{dam}]$ [where phth, am and dam stands for phthalate ion, aromatic amine and diamine, respectively]. Elemental analysis, conductivity and molecular weight studies confirm the above formulae. The magnetic and spectroscopic studies indicate that all the complexes can be assigned as having nearly planar geometries. The absorption bands have been assigned and the values of the ligand field stabilisation energies are calculated.

A survey of literature indicates that a large number of amine complexes of first row transition elements have been prepared and studied with almost all possible inorganic anions, but little work is reported with their organic salts. During our attempts to study the effect of organic anion on the co-ordination number and the stereochemistry, a number of Copper(II), Nickel(II), Cobalt(II), Iron(II) and Manganese(II) complexes were prepared with phthalimide, succinimide, oxalate, formate, benzoate and succinate ions¹⁻⁶. With a view to extend the work further now complexes of transition metal phthalates are being prepared and studied. The phthalate ion which contains two COO^- groups is expected to act as a bidentate ligand itself, besides neutralizing the charge of the metal, thus making only two other co-ordination centers available for the incoming ligands. The present paper records the preparation of some fourteen complexes of Copper(II) phthalate with aromatic amine like aniline, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidine, α -, β - and γ -picolines, pyridine, quinoline and some diamines like ethylene and propylenediamine, *o*-phenanthroline and 2,2'-dipyridyl. A study of their conductivity, molecular weight, Infrared, magnetic susceptibility electronic and electron spin resonance spectra has been carried out and result interpreted in a consistent manner.

Experimental

Preparation : All complexes were prepared by adding an excess of amine to copper phthalate suspended in absolute ethanol, refluxing the solution for a number of hours and crystallising out the complex from the solution. The result of the elemental analysis are listed in Table 1.

Conductivity and Molecular Weights : The conductivities were measured in the nitrobenzene at a

conc. of $10^{-3}M$ on a Philips P.R. 9500 magic eye type instrument and molecular weight in formamide cryscopically and values are given in Table 1.

I.R. Spectra : These were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 221 in the region $4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The experimental data are not listed in the paper but can be obtained from the authors, if required.

Magnetic Susceptibility Measurements : Determination of magnetic susceptibilities were made on powdered samples by using the standard Gouy method, and the μ_{eff} values are given in Table 2.

Electronic Spectra : These were obtained on a Cary 14 recording instrument in the range 200-2000 nm and absorption maxima listed in Table 2.

Electron Spin Resonance Spectra : These were obtained on a varian V_sQ band spectrophotometer using polycrystalline samples.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis show the molecular formulae to be $[\text{Cu}(\text{phth})\text{am}_2 \text{ or } \text{dam}]$, while the molar conductance and molecular weight values suggest that the complexes are non-electrolytes and hence the phthalate ion is also co-ordinated (occupying any two adjacent positions in the co-ordination sphere). The complexes are thus tetra-co-ordinated in all the cases, the co-ordination of amine being confirmed by the following data on the infrared spectra.

I.R. Spectra of Pyridine Complexes : The infrared spectra of pyridine and its complexes with transition metals have been extensively studied⁷⁻⁹, and it is

* Dr. S. T. Spees, Professor of Chemistry, Michigan State University, East Lansing, Michigan, U.S.A. 48823—has helped in obtaining ESR spectra of complexes.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTANCE AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT DATA

Compound No.	Formula	%Cu	%C	%H	%N	Mol. Wt.	Molar Conductance
1.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(<i>o</i> -tol) ₂]	14.31 (14.39)	62.90 (62.56)	4.78 (4.98)	6.54 (6.34)	425 (441)	0.251
2.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(<i>m</i> -tol) ₂]	14.66 (14.39)	62.80 (62.56)	4.72 (4.98)	6.74 (6.34)	385 (441)	0.242
3.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(<i>p</i> -tol) ₂]	14.70 (14.39)	62.90 (62.56)	4.78 (4.98)	6.54 (6.34)	—	—
4.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(<i>py</i>) ₂].2H ₂ O	15.23 (15.06)	54.57 (54.13)	3.97 (4.27)	6.70 (6.64)	390 (421)	0.612
5.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(<i>an</i>) ₂]	15.10 (15.35)	60.58 (60.96)	5.00 (4.35)	6.98 (6.76)	397 (413)	0.700
6.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(<i>qui</i>) ₂]	13.95 (13.64)	66.96 (66.81)	3.46 (3.70)	5.62 (5.76)	460 (485)	—
7.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(α -pic) ₂]	15.01 (15.35)	61.58 (60.95)	4.60 (4.35)	7.05 (6.77)	—	0.521
8.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(β -pic) ₂]	15.60 (15.35)	61.22 (60.95)	4.52 (4.35)	7.08 (6.77)	335 (413)	0.251
9.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(γ -pic) ₂]	15.04 (15.35)	61.50 (60.95)	4.70 (4.35)	7.25 (6.77)	—	0.158
10.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(<i>morp</i>) ₂]	15.32 (15.81)	51.52 (50.85)	5.19 (5.45)	7.42 (6.97)	355 (401)	0.194
11.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(<i>pn</i>)].2H ₂ O	18.20 (18.81)	43.12 (49.66)	5.60 (5.33)	8.02 (8.29)	305 (337)	0.295
12.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(<i>en</i>)].2H ₂ O	18.91 (19.62)	41.71 (41.11)	5.02 (4.94)	9.22 (8.65)	298 (323)	0.295
13.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(<i>o</i> -phen)]	14.72 (15.59)	61.51 (61.81)	3.15 (2.94)	4.05 (3.42)	330 (407)	0.500
14.	[Cu(C ₉ H ₄ O ₄)(<i>dipy</i> .)]	15.91 (16.52)	60.20 (59.16)	4.08 (3.11)	8.50 (7.26)	—	0.215

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENT, ELECTRONIC AND ELECTRON SPIN RESONANCE SPECTRAL DATA

Compound No.	μ_{eff} B.M.	λ_{max} in nm	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	10Dq (cm ⁻¹)	gI	gII	g ave.	μ_{eff} from ESR
1.	1.931	760 800 (sh)	13,171 12,500 (sh)	131.0	2.223	2.122	2.189	1.896
2.	1.940	762 805 (sh)	13,122 12,422 (sh)	131.2	—	—	—	—
3.	1.946	769 812 (sh)	13,003 12,302 (sh)	130.0	—	—	—	—
4.	1.933	766 810 (sh)	13,054 12,345 (sh)	130.5	2.205	2.160	2.190	1.896
5.	1.887	759 810 (sh)	13,176 12,345 (sh)	131.7	2.228	2.130	2.195	1.901
6.	1.905	762 802 (sh)	13,122 12,468 (sh)	131.2	2.200	2.170	2.190	1.896
7.	1.920	755 802 (sh)	13,249 12,468 (sh)	132.4	2.220	2.150	2.196	1.901
8.	1.932	768 810 (sh)	13,020 12,345 (sh)	130.2	—	—	—	—
9.	1.922	760	13,171	131.7	—	—	—	—
10.	1.885	778 802 (sh)	12,853 12,468	128.5	—	—	—	—
11.	1.840	570 408 (sh)	17,543 20,813 (sh)	175.4	—	—	—	—
12.	1.844	576 495 (sh)	17,534 20,202 (sh)	175.3	2.210	2.170	2.196	1.901
13.	1.892	581 482 (sh)	17,227 20,746 (sh)	172.2	—	—	—	—
14.	1.879	568	17,588	175.8	—	—	—	—

found that most of the band frequencies of the free bases are either split or shifted to higher wave numbers on co-ordination, as a result of the tightening of the aromatic ring¹⁰⁻¹². In all the complexes

the group of five bands between 990-1031 cm⁻¹ and the 8 a band (occurring as a shoulder at 1538 cm⁻¹ in free pyridine) is shifted to higher wave number in support of co-ordination.

I.R. Spectra of Picoline Complexes : Theoretically the complexes of picoline have essentially the same i.r. spectra as those of pyridine. The only difference being in the appearance of some new bands due to methyl groups. Most of the important vibrational modes show positive shift as in the case of pyridine complexes, on co-ordination¹³.

However, the bands due to asymmetric and symmetric deformation modes of methyl group, around 1445 and 1386 cm^{-1} remain unaltered, which is due to the fact that the methyl groups are not directly attached to nitrogen and hence not involved in complex formation.

I.R. Spectra of Aniline and Toluidine Complexes : All the complexes absorb near 3300 cm^{-1} region due to NH stretching frequencies. The same set of band in the free ligand occurs in the range 3400-3450 cm^{-1} and this negative shift of about 100-150 cm^{-1} is a result of co-ordination.

I.R. Spectra of Ethylene and Propylene Diamine Complexes : The vibrational frequencies of the present complexes have been assigned according to that reported in literature. Upon co-ordination the NH stretching frequency usually splits and shifts to a lower value by about 100-200 cm^{-1} . The skeleton vibrations in the free ligand have been observed at 1130, 1095 and 830 cm^{-1} . But upon co-ordination only one of these vibrations is observed as a strong band at 1060 cm^{-1} [in ethylenediamine complexes] and at 1070 cm^{-1} [in propylenediamine complex]¹⁴.

I.R. Spectra of 2,2'-dipyridyl and o-phenanthroline Complexes : The i.r. spectra of these complexes also show shifts in the ligand bands upon co-ordination, when compared with free bases^{15,16}. The spectra of 2,2'-dipyridyl complex is more complicated due to the splitting and appearance of new bands, but the bands at 1576, 1137, 1087 and 400 cm^{-1} of free ligand show a constant positive shift. The strong bands at 855, 740, 1626, 1592 and 1565 cm^{-1} of free o-phenanthroline which are due to the C-H out of plane bending vibrations and ring stretching shifts to lower frequencies. The positions and intensities of the other bands are not changed much, due to the fact that the total electron density over the ring system does not change much upon co-ordination.

I.R. Spectra of Phthalate Ion : As reported in our previous publications, in most of the cases the organic anion was also found to be co-ordinated to the metal, acting either as a mono or a bidentate ligand depending upon the number of donor atoms present. The phthalate ion, in the present case is also co-ordinated, a fact suggested by conductivity and further confirmed by i.r. spectra of the complexes, where the asymmetric and symmetric COO-stretching frequencies are observed between 1690-1702 cm^{-1} and 1417-1454 cm^{-1} respectively characteristic of co-ordinated carboxylate ion¹⁷.

All the complexes are paramagnetic as indicated by their $\mu_{\text{effective}}$ values which are close to 1.90

B.M. These values suggest square planar structures, as in that case there is no significant orbital contribution to moment apart from that contributed in second order by spin-orbit coupling¹⁷. At the same time, tetrahedral structure can be eliminated, as these would have a T2 ground state and would be expected to have moments larger than 2.0 B.M.

The diffuse reflectance spectra of these complexes shows at least two bands in the visible region of the spectrum. The aromatic mono amine complexes have a band around 13,000 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at lower energy side, while the diamine complexes have a band at 17,000 with a shoulder at higher energy side. This type of spectra is again consistent with a square planar geometry of the complex¹⁸. The position of these main absorption bands is directly related to ligand field energy and this clearly shows that the aromatic amines are weaker ligands than diamines.

The ESR spectra of the complexes have been obtained and these show two sharp signals characteristic of Copper(II). The measurement of the areas under the two parts in the ratio 2 : 1 corresponding to gII and gI gives the former at comparatively low fields and latter at higher fields and the values lie in the range 2.08-2.20. These are consistent with magnetically dilute Copper(II) environments and suggest mononuclear structures for the complexes^{19,20}. The average g-values have been used to calculate $\mu_{\text{effective}}$ and these show a good agreement with the values obtained by Gouy technique.

The above data thus suggest square planar structure for the complex in which two adjacent positions are occupied by phthalate ion and other two positions are taken up by either two molecules of aromatic amine or one molecule of diamine. The X-ray studies of the complexes are now being undertaken in order to conclusively establish their structure.

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